

1 **Interaction between waves and gravity currents:**
2 **description of turbulence in a simple numerical model**

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6 Received: 11 May 2016

7 **Abstract** Effects of surface waves on gravity current propagation are studied by
8 means of a numerical model. The adopted modeling approach couples a Boussinesq-
9 type of model for surface waves and a gravity current model for stratified flows. In
10 particular two different turbulence closure models are introduced which take into
11 account subgrid turbulence and an additional depth-constant eddy-viscosity. The
12 turbulence parameters are calibrated by means of experimental data on the time
13 evolution of the heavy front, obtained both in the absence and in the presence of
14 regular surface waves. Velocity fields, heavy and light front position, shear stresses,
15 vorticity and entrainment calculated by the model are analyzed.

16 The turbulence closure which includes both uniform and Smagorinsky type
17 eddy viscosity allows a better description of the actual gravity current propaga-

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18 tion. In particular, the results highlight the fact that the presence of the oscillatory
19 motion causes, simultaneously, a reduction in turbulence and an increase in the
20 mixing of heavy and light fluids. Such a result is in agreement with the experi-
21 mental observations.

22 **Keywords** density currents · wave motion · turbulence

23 1 Introduction

24 Buoyancy driven flows in the presence of surface waves are common in estuarine
25 and coastal regions, in natural, urban and industrial zones [33]. The dynamics of
26 gravity currents in the absence of waves has been often investigated by observing
27 the well-known lock-exchange phenomenon [9,23,24], i.e. two fluids, having dif-
28 ferent densities initially separated by a vertical gate, which move toward a more
29 stable condition with the lighter fluid flowing at the top and the higher density
30 fluid at the bottom. A fundamental description of gravity currents and intrusions
31 can be found in [35], where a wide variety of applications was investigated. 3D
32 lock-exchange gravity currents were studied in [11] by means of experimental and
33 numerical simulations. Furthermore, an innovative numerical Lattice-Boltzmann
34 method was used in [10,30] to simulate such a phenomenon. The mixing mecha-
35 nism, related to lock-exchange gravity currents, was studied through laboratory
36 gravity currents [7] and 3D numerical models [27,28].

37 The effect of surface waves on the propagation of gravity currents has not been
38 extensively investigated yet, as noted in [3]. Among the few available studies, [22]
39 developed an asymptotic theory for the spreading of a layer of heavy immiscible
40 liquid at the bottom due to the effects of surface waves. These authors considered a

41 multiple scale perturbation analysis, by assuming that surface waves and gravity
42 currents act at different time scales, since sea waves are faster than buoyancy-
43 driven flows and streaming effects. Evolution equations of profile distribution of
44 the heavy liquid are obtained as a function of slow-time variables. They found
45 that the streaming current, induced by surface waves, usually predominates and
46 drives the heavy liquid to propagate together with surface waves. In the case of
47 standing waves, the alternating component of the streaming current can induce
48 the development of an undulating interface between the two fluids. The formation
49 of such an undulation can dramatically change the local structure of mass trans-
50 port near the bottom and it is related to the presence of circulating cells, whose
51 characteristics depend on the thickness of the dense layer.

52 [31] studied the evolution of the release of a heavy liquid at the bottom of sur-
53 face waves. They showed that, after the initial fall, the gravity current propagates
54 with two fronts moving in opposite directions, whose overall length was weakly
55 affected by wave action, since it is mainly determined by buoyancy. The position
56 of the middle point and the shape of the heavy front were significantly affected
57 by the presence of surface waves: i) Stokes drift dominates for long waves and the
58 middle point of the heavy liquid is moved downstream; ii) the Eulerian-averaged
59 velocity is most important near the bed for short waves and the gravity current
60 moves upstream, opposite to the direction of wave propagation. Finally, [31] found
61 that the centre of the current is advected at a fraction of the Lagrangian velocity
62 at the bed.

63 More recently, [21] proposed a numerical model to study the combined surface
64 waves - gravity current flow. The model tries to fill the gap between two-layer
65 shallow water models [12] and more complex LES and DNS models able to mimic

66 the complete hydrodynamics of the non-homogeneous density flow [25,8]. The
67 model decouples buoyancy-driven flow and wave motion, by separating the orbital
68 velocity from the gravity current velocity. Such a model was derived under the
69 assumption of inviscid flow and free slip condition at the bottom. A preliminary
70 validation of the numerical model was carried out by means of the experimental
71 data of [21]. In both experimental and numerical data, the heavy front was slower
72 in the presence of waves with respect to the calm water case. The behaviour of the
73 undulations predicted by the model at the interface between the two fluids, in the
74 rear part of the heavy front, was qualitatively in agreement with the experimental
75 observations, notwithstanding the fact that turbulent effects were neglected in
76 the gravity current model. However, the velocity of the heavy front computed
77 by the numerical model was overpredicted as a consequence of the inviscid flow
78 assumption.

79 In the present work, such an assumption has been eliminated. Turbulence has
80 been modeled by two alternative formulations: the first considers only a Smagorin-
81 sky type eddy viscosity [32]; in the second formulation, eddy viscosity is the sum
82 of both a Smagorinsky component and a depth-constant component. The ratio-
83 nale behind the latter formulation is that the presence of an additional uniform
84 viscosity component should better simulate the background turbulence due to
85 the combined flow resulting from gravity currents interacting with surface waves.
86 Both formulations have been considered for each of the tests carried out, in order
87 to verify which turbulence closure is the most reliable one.

88 Gravity currents generated by a lock-exchange scheme are studied here, since
89 such a scheme presents a constant-speed phase and it has been studied compre-
90 hensively in scientific literature.

91 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed numerical
 92 approach, focusing on the turbulence model. Section 3 presents the benchmark
 93 experimental data, the setup and the calibration of the model. Section 4 discusses
 94 the results of the numerical model both in the absence and in the presence of
 95 surface waves, by focusing on the dynamics of the density, velocity, vorticity and
 96 shear stress fields. Results are also shown on the entrainment process. Concluding
 97 remarks are given in Section 5.

98 2 Proposed numerical approach

99 A new numerical model has been developed to analyze the combined two-dimensional
 100 flow of gravity currents and free surface waves. The governing equations are ob-
 101 tained under the assumption of Boussinesq gravity currents. The adopted reference
 102 system is shown in Figure 1 where the two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate sys-
 103 tem (x, z) is located on the still water level, from which the water depth h is
 104 measured. By using an approach similar to that in [35], the continuity equation,
 105 the two momentum Reynolds-Averaged equations and the density transport equa-
 106 tion are:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \frac{du}{dt} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz}) \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \frac{dw}{dt} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz}) - \rho g \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = \kappa \left(\frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (4)$$

110 where u and w are the horizontal and vertical components of ensemble-averaged
 111 velocity; p is the total pressure; τ_{xz} and τ'_{xz} are the viscous and turbulent stresses

Fig. 1 Sketch of gravity current propagation under surface waves with indication of the reference system and of the main variables.

112 respectively; ρ is the local density, whose value is comprised between the density of
 113 the ambient fluid ρ_0 and the density of the heaviest fluid $\rho_1 > \rho_0$; g is the gravity
 114 acceleration; κ is the diffusion coefficient of the solute (e.g. sodium chloride in the
 115 case analysed in this paper), which is equal to zero in the case of immiscible fluids.

116 Modelling the surface wave motion in a lock-exchange release is a complex
 117 task, which, thanks to the adopted Boussinesq approximation i.e. $\gamma = \rho_0/\rho_1 \sim 1$,
 118 is tackled here by considering that surface waves are not influenced by gravity
 119 currents. Indeed the phase speed of surface waves is proportional to gravity (g),
 120 whereas the bulk velocity of the gravity current is proportional to the reduced
 121 gravity g' , since $g' \ll g$ as a consequence of the Boussinesq approximation. As
 122 a consequence of that it is possible to decouple the homogeneous density wave
 123 motion and the gravity current propagation forced by actual density gradients, by
 124 neglecting, at leading order, the influence of buoyancy on the wave field. Such an
 125 assumption is also confirmed by the present experimental data.

126 It follows that the total velocity field \mathbf{u} is obtained by linearly adding up the
 127 effects of the external wave motion and of the gravity current:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_B + \mathbf{u}_d \quad (5)$$

128 where $\mathbf{u}_B \equiv (u_B, w_B)$ is the wave orbital velocity, which is independent from
 129 the gradient of ρ and it is calculated through a Boussinesq-type wave model for
 130 homogeneous flow, and the gravity current $\mathbf{u}_d \equiv (u_d, w_d)$ which is evaluated as a
 131 function of the pressure field induced by both buoyancy and waves.

132 A splitting procedure between the orbital wave motion and the gravity current
 133 is applied to eqs. (1) and (2), giving respectively:

$$\frac{\partial(u_B + u_d)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(w_B + w_d)}{\partial z} = \left(\frac{\partial u_B}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w_B}{\partial z} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u_d}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w_d}{\partial z} \right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

134

$$\begin{aligned} & \rho_0 \frac{d(u_B + u_d)}{dt} + \frac{\partial(p_B + p_d)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [(\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_B + (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_d] = \\ & \left[\rho_0 \frac{du_B}{dt} + \frac{\partial p_B}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_B \right] + \left[\rho_0 \frac{du_d}{dt} + \frac{\partial p_d}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_d \right] \\ & + u_B \frac{\partial u_d}{\partial x} + u_d \frac{\partial u_B}{\partial x} + w_B \frac{\partial u_d}{\partial z} + w_d \frac{\partial u_B}{\partial z} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

135 in which pressure and shear stresses are split similarly to the velocity. Further
 136 details on such components will be given in Section 2.1 and 2.2, when describing
 137 the two decoupled models.

138 Since the above velocity decomposition is adopted, the horizontal momentum
 139 equation presents mixed convective terms, which are reported in the last row of
 140 eq. (7). As these mixed terms are neglected in the proposed model, the model
 141 may fail when it is applied to reproduce highly nonlinear phenomena. In the lock-
 142 exchange process, the greatest nonlinearities occur during the initial acceleration
 143 phase after the gate opening. Therefore, it is expected that the proposed model

144 is more reliable once the constant - speed phase is reached. An analysis on the
145 importance of neglected convective terms has been carried out. The results confirm
146 the above limit of the model, particularly up to the point when the distance
147 between the heavy and lighter front is similar to the value of the water depth.
148 After such an initial stage, the mixed convective terms are negligible and do not
149 influence the physics of the gravity currents under surface waves.

150 The modelling procedure is schematized by the flow-chart shown in Figure 2,
151 in which the incident surface wave height (H) and period (T) represent the input
152 of the Boussinesq-type wave propagation model. The initial density distribution
153 corresponds to a lock-exchange configuration, i.e. the fluid with density ρ_1 is sep-
154 arated by a fluid having density $\rho_0 < \rho_1$ by a vertical sluice gate. Such a density
155 distribution, along with the orbital velocity field \mathbf{u}_B and the free surface elevation
156 due to the waves ζ_B , are entered into the gravity current model, which calculates
157 the evolution of the total velocity \mathbf{u} and of the density distribution.

158 2.1 Model for surface waves

159 A one-dimensional weakly dispersive fully nonlinear Boussinesq-type model [20,
160 13] has been adopted here to describe the hydrodynamics of surface waves. Such a
161 model was originally derived to describe surf zone hydrodynamics and it has been
162 recently extended to deal with two-dimensional horizontal problems [37].

163 On the basis of scaling arguments for relatively shallow water wave propaga-
164 tion, two dimensionless parameters are adopted, namely the dispersive parameter
165 $\mu = kh$ and the nonlinear parameter $\delta = a/h$, where $a = H_w/2$ is the surface
166 wave amplitude. Since the surface wave model is weakly dispersive, only terms up

Fig. 2 Flowchart of the proposed approach for modelling gravity currents under surface waves.

Input variables are: characteristics of the regular wave motion (i.e. wave period T and wave height H) and initial density distribution. Such a distribution is characterized by two uniform zones having density ρ_0 and ρ_1 respectively, as in the lock exchange initial setup.

167 to $O(\mu^2)$ are retained, whereas the fact that the model is fully nonlinear means
 168 that no assumptions are made about the order of magnitude of δ . It is assumed
 169 also that the flow is irrotational only outside the surf zone, that is wave breaking
 170 is assumed to be the unique source of vorticity within the flow. Within the surf
 171 zone the velocity field is influenced by the effects of breaking-induced vorticity
 172 and the vorticity transport equation is solved analytically. The amount of vortic-
 173 ity introduced by the breaking process is determined through a similarity with the
 174 hydraulic jump, by using the surface roller concept [34]. The governing equations

175 of the Boussinesq-type wave model, applied here, have been derived in [20]. In
 176 particular, it is possible to separate the wave related horizontal velocity (u_B) into
 177 a potential component u_p and a rotational component u_r , which is function of
 178 surface wave related vorticity.

179 It is assumed [36] that potential velocity component can be represented as a
 180 sum of the mean potential velocity \bar{u}_p and of a quadratic function of vertical coor-
 181 dinate z . Consequently, the total wave related horizontal velocity can be expressed
 182 as follows

$$u_B = \bar{u}_p + \mu^2 (h\bar{u}_p)_{xx} \left(\frac{\Delta_1}{2} - z \right) + \frac{\mu^2}{2} (\bar{u}_p)_{xx} \left(\frac{\Delta_2}{3} - z^2 \right) + u_r + O(\mu^4) \quad (8)$$

183 where the subscript x represents partial derivative along the horizontal direction.
 184 In the present case, $u_r = 0$ since waves are non-breaking; Δ_1 and Δ_2 are coefficients
 185 given by the following expressions:

$$\Delta_1 = \delta\zeta_B - h, \quad \Delta_2 = \delta^2\zeta_B^2 - \delta\zeta_B h + h^2 \quad (9)$$

186 in which ζ_B is the free surface elevation under homogeneous flow conditions.

187 The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations, used in the derivation of the
 188 adopted Boussinesq-type of model, can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial u_B}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w_B}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{du_B}{dt} + \frac{\partial p_B}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_B = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{dw_B}{dt} + \frac{\partial p_B}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_B + \rho_0 g = 0 \quad (12)$$

191 where eqs. (10) and (11) correspond, respectively, to the wave component of eq. (6)
 192 and (7); eq. (12) is the vertical momentum equation used to derive the wave
 193 component of pressure p_B . All these equations are valid under a uniform density
 194 condition.

195 In order to obtain the Boussinesq-type wave model [20], such equations can be
 196 integrated over the depth and it is possible to apply the kinematic and dynamic
 197 boundary conditions at the bottom and at the free surface. Consequently the
 198 following equations can be obtained, as a function of surface elevation ζ_B and of
 199 depth-averaged horizontal orbital velocity, \bar{u} :

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_B}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\bar{u}(h + \delta \zeta_B)] = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{u}_t + \delta \bar{u} \bar{u}_x + \zeta_{Bx} + \mu^2 \left[\left(B - \frac{1}{3} \right) h^2 \bar{u}_{xxt} - \frac{1}{2} h h_{xx} \bar{u}_t - h h_x \bar{u}_{xt} \right] \\ & + B \mu^2 h^2 \zeta_{xxx} + \delta \mu^2 \left[-\frac{1}{3} h^2 \bar{u} \bar{u}_{xxx} - h \zeta_{Bx} \bar{u}_{xt} + \frac{1}{3} h^2 \bar{u}_x \bar{u}_{xx} - \frac{2}{3} h \zeta_B \bar{u}_{xxt} \right. \\ & - \frac{3}{2} h h_{xx} \bar{u} \bar{u}_x - \frac{1}{2} h h_{xx} \bar{u}^2 - h h_x \bar{u} \bar{u}_{xx} - \zeta_B h_x \bar{u}_{xt} - h_x \zeta_{Bx} \bar{u}_t \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \zeta_B h_{xx} \bar{u}_t + B h^2 (\bar{u} \bar{u}_x)_{xx} \left. \right] + \delta^2 \mu^2 \left[\frac{1}{6} \zeta_B^2 \bar{u}_{xxt} - \frac{1}{3} h \zeta_B \bar{u}_x \bar{u}_{xx} \right. \\ & - \frac{1}{3} h \bar{u}_{xx} (\zeta_B \bar{u})_x + h (\zeta_B \bar{u}_x^2)_x - \frac{1}{2} (\zeta_B^2 \bar{u}_{xt})_x - \frac{2}{3} h (\zeta_B \bar{u} \bar{u}_{xx})_x \\ & - \zeta_{Bx} h_{xx} \bar{u}^2 - \zeta_B h_x \bar{u} \bar{u}_{xx} - \frac{1}{2} \zeta_B h_{xxx} \bar{u}^2 - \frac{3}{2} \zeta_B h_{xx} \bar{u} \bar{u}_x - \zeta_{Bx} h_x \bar{u} \bar{u}_x \left. \right] \\ & + \delta^3 \mu^2 \left[-\frac{1}{3} \zeta_B^2 \bar{u} \bar{u}_{xxx} - \zeta_B \zeta_{Bx} \bar{u} \bar{u}_{xx} + \zeta_B \zeta_{Bx} \bar{u}_x^2 + \frac{1}{3} \zeta_B^2 \bar{u}_x \bar{u}_{xx} \right] \\ & + [\delta (\Delta M)_x + \mu^2 (\Delta P)_{xxt} - \mu^2 D_s + \delta \mu^2 (\Delta M_1)_x + \delta \mu^2 D_w \\ & + \delta \mu^2 D_{uw}] (h + \delta \zeta_B)^{-1} + O(\mu^4) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

200 where the subscript t represents partial derivative over the time; B is a coefficient
 201 which allows for the enhancement of the dispersion characteristics of the model in
 202 deeper water, with $B = 1/15$ suggested by [17]; the terms $(\Delta M)_x, (\Delta P)_{xxt}, (\Delta M_1)_x,$
 203 D_w, D_s and D_{uw} are the breaking terms, function of the rotational velocity u_r .
 204 In the present work all these terms are equal to zero, as well as vorticity and
 205 rotational velocity.

206 For the numerical solution of eqs. (13) and (14), the Adams-Bashforth-Moulton
 207 scheme is used since it gives good stability properties [29]. Such a scheme consists
 208 of two stages: a first-attempt predictor step, which is accurate up to 3th order,
 209 and an iterative corrector step which is accurate up to 4th order.

210 At the offshore boundary outgoing waves are allowed to leave the domain
 211 by using an absorbing-generating boundary condition [5], while at the onshore
 212 boundary a sponge layer is used in order to dissipate the wave motion at the
 213 shoreward boundary of the domain [20].

214 Starting from the solution of the above eqs. (13) and (14) of the model, which
 215 gives ζ_B and \bar{u} , it is possible to extract information on the horizontal component
 216 of orbital flow motion u_B by applying eq. (8) with $u_r = 0$.

217 Similarly, the vertical component of surface wave related velocity (w_B) can be
 218 obtained, by inserting u_B , calculated using eq. (8), inside the continuity eq. (10):

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_B = & -(\bar{u}_p)_x(z+h) - 2\bar{u}_p h_x - \mu^2(h\bar{u}_p)_{xxx} \left[\frac{\Delta_1}{2}(z+h) - \frac{z^2}{2} + \frac{h^2}{2} \right] \\
 & - \mu^2(h\bar{u}_p)_{xx} \left[\frac{(\Delta_1)_x}{2}(z+h) + 2hh_x + \Delta_1 h_x \right] \\
 & - \frac{\mu^2}{2}(\bar{u}_p)_{xxx} \left[\frac{\Delta_2}{3}(z+h) - \frac{z^3}{3} - \frac{h^3}{3} \right] \\
 & - \frac{\mu^2}{2}(\bar{u}_p)_{xx} \left[\frac{(\Delta_2)_x}{3}(z+h) - 2h^2 h_x + \frac{2}{3}\Delta_2 h_x \right] + O(\mu^4) \quad (15)
 \end{aligned}$$

219 2.2 Model for gravity currents

220 The orbital velocity field, $\mathbf{u}_B \equiv (u_B, w_B)$, and the free surface elevation, ζ_B ,
 221 obtained through the above wave model, are the inputs of the proposed gravity
 222 current model, which is a modified version of the one proposed in [21]. In particular,

223 here a viscous flow is considered and a turbulence closure is included to better
 224 simulate the full depth lock exchange phenomenon. A further assumption is that
 225 the presence of a spatial variability of density may influence the flow only through
 226 modification of the pressure field. Hence, the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
 227 momentum equations, i.e. eqs. (2) and (3), are rewritten in terms of a new pressure
 228 term related to stratification, called $p_d = p - p_B$, where p_B is the value of the wave-
 229 related dynamic in homogeneous non-stratified conditions.

230 The adopted splitting procedure between the wave related velocity $\mathbf{u}_B \equiv$
 231 (u_B, w_B) and the gravity current velocity $\mathbf{u}_d \equiv (u_d, w_d)$ has been already in-
 232 troduced in eqs. (6) and (7), i.e. in the continuity and horizontal momentum equa-
 233 tions. The density-related continuity and horizontal momentum equations which
 234 are extracted from eqs. (6) and (7) can be written as follows

$$\frac{\partial u_d}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w_d}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{du_d}{dt} + \frac{\partial p_d}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_d = 0 \quad (17)$$

235
 236 where the last two terms on the left-hand-side of eq. (17) represent the viscous
 237 and turbulent shear stresses related to gravity currents. Such stresses are modeled
 238 by means of the kinematic and eddy viscosity, ν and ν_t respectively. Thus eq. (17)
 239 reads:

$$\frac{\partial u_d}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial u_d^2}{\partial x} + w_d \frac{\partial u_d}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p_d}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[(\nu + \nu_t) \left(\frac{\partial u_d}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w_d}{\partial x} \right) \right] = 0 \quad (18)$$

240 The pressure variable p_d can be computed on the basis of a properly decomposed
 241 vertical momentum equation, obtained by subtracting eq. (12) from the total ver-
 242 tical momentum eq. (3), and by applying the Boussinesq approximation:

$$\rho_0 \frac{dw}{dt} + \rho g - \rho_0 \left(\frac{dw_B}{dt} + g \right) + \frac{\partial p_d}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [(\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz}) - (\tau_{xz} + \tau'_{xz})_B] = 0 \quad (19)$$

243 The pressure term p_d , due to the in-homogeneous density field, can be calculated
 244 by integrating eq. (19) over the water depth, i.e. between the bottom ($z = -h$)
 245 and the free surface ($z = \zeta$):

$$p_d = \int_{-h}^{\zeta} -\Delta\rho g - \rho_0 \left(\frac{dw}{dt} - \frac{dw_B}{dt} \right) + \rho_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\nu + \nu_t) \left(\frac{\partial u_d}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w_d}{\partial x} \right) \right] dz \quad (20)$$

246 in which $\Delta\rho = \rho - \rho_0$ is the local density variation with respect to the initial
 247 value ρ_0 of the lighter fluid. Eq. (20) is numerically integrated, by means of the
 248 trapezoidal rule [29], between the free surface ζ , where the pressure p_d is assumed
 249 equal to zero, and the bottom $z = -h$.

250 Following the hypothesis at the basis of the derivation of the proposed model, it
 251 is assumed that at leading order the wave motion dominates and the contribution
 252 due to density variations is negligible, i.e. $\zeta_d \ll \zeta_B$. Nevertheless, the contribution
 253 to the free surface elevation ζ_d must also be included when computing eq. (20) to
 254 find p_d . Such a contribution is calculated by integrating eq. (16) along the water
 255 column and by applying the well-known kinematic boundary conditions at the free
 256 surface and at the bottom, thus obtaining:

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_d}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{-h}^{\zeta} u_d dz = 0 \quad (21)$$

257 The unknown variables of the gravity current model are p_d , u_d , w_d , ρ and ζ_d .
 258 All the other variables are outputs of the previous Boussinesq-type surface wave
 259 model. Therefore a total of 5 equations are solved. In particular, w_d is calculated by
 260 spatially integrating eq. (16); p_d by integrating eq. (20) over the depth; u_d , ρ and ζ_d
 261 are estimated by iteratively solving eqs. (18), (4) and (21), which all contain time
 262 derivatives. Similarly to the wave model, also here the Adams-Bashforth-Moulton
 263 scheme is used for time-stepping.

264 In order to solve eq. (18), a free slip boundary condition is used at the bottom.
265 Such a condition allows the model to be efficient since it does not need a very
266 refined grid, with respect to a more rigorous no-slip condition which would need a
267 very fine discretization close to the bed. Preliminary tests have been carried out
268 by considering also a friction velocity at the bottom, proportional to the drag co-
269 efficient. It has been found that the advantages of using such a modified boundary
270 condition at the bottom are not significant compared to the velocity field predicted
271 by the model with the mere simpler slip boundary condition adopted here.

272 2.3 Turbulence closure

273 The use of a 2D model for gravity currents may cause a non-realistic simulation
274 of the dynamics of the turbulent structures at the interface between the two fluids
275 (e.g. Kelvin-Helmholtz billows), with respect to 3D models. In particular, in 2D
276 models such turbulent structures tend to become bigger than those present in ac-
277 tual gravity current propagation [26]. In the proposed model, which is designed for
278 engineering applications, we decide to partially overcome such a limit by carrying
279 out an adequate calibration of some simple turbulent closure formulations. This
280 allows to achieve a reasonable comparison between the modeled gravity current
281 and reality. Such a 2D calibrated model simulates K-H structures which do not
282 detach from the front between the two fluids, thus giving a behaviour qualitatively
283 similar to laboratory gravity currents [21].

284 As shown in eqs. (18) and (20), the proposed approach for simulating buoyancy-
285 driven flows considers the effects of turbulence by means of the eddy viscosity
286 concept. This kind of turbulent closure is quite simple, if compared to other more

287 physically based approaches, such as $k - \epsilon$ or $k - \omega$ methods [2], and it has been
 288 widely tested in both steady and oscillatory flow conditions [32,6,14,1].

289 In particular, in the present work two kinds of eddy viscosity have been adopted.
 290 In the first approach, called formulation ‘A’, the eddy viscosity is estimated on
 291 the basis of the Smagorinsky approach for sub-grid scale turbulence (SGS) [32],
 292 as a function of the local derivatives of the velocity field and of the local grid size:

$$\nu_{t,A} = C_s \Delta x \Delta z \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial z}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}\right)^2} \quad (22)$$

293 where C_s is a parameter to be determined through calibration, Δx and Δz are the
 294 dimension of the numerical grid along the horizontal and the vertical directions,
 295 respectively. Using such a formulation the small (sub-grid) scales are assumed to
 296 be in equilibrium, thus energy production and dissipation balanced. This kind of
 297 approach is widely adopted in large-eddy simulations (LES) in which the effect of
 298 large scales is directly computed [6].

299 Since the formulation A is a mere SGS formulation, it may not be capable of
 300 taking into account larger scale effects due to the interaction between the orbital
 301 motion and the gravity current. Thus an alternative formulation has been tested
 302 (called ‘B’), where a depth-uniform background eddy viscosity is added to the SGS
 303 Smagorinsky eddy viscosity of formulation A:

$$\nu_{t,B} = C_u h \sqrt{g' h} + C_s \Delta x \Delta z \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial z}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}\right)^2} \quad (23)$$

304 where g' is the reduced gravity, defined as $g(\rho_1 - \rho_0)/\rho_0$, and C_u is an additional
 305 calibration coefficient. The parameter C_s is similar to the one used in the purely
 306 Smagorinsky formulation (eq. 22) but its values are expected to be lower, due to
 307 the contribution of the depth-uniform viscosity component.

308 After a calibration of the two parameters C_s and C_u , the differences between
309 the two proposed formulations (A and B respectively) are discussed in the following
310 by analyzing the hydrodynamics of the propagation of gravity currents both in the
311 absence and in the presence of surface waves. In particular, results are presented on
312 the kinematics of the front propagation, density distribution, velocity and vorticity
313 field, shear stresses and entrainment.

314 **3 Calibration of the model**

315 **3.1 Benchmark experiments**

316 A laboratory dataset of lock-exchange experiments performed within a wave flume
317 has been used as a benchmark in order to calibrate the parameters of the two
318 turbulence models described above. The experiments have been carried out in a
319 wave flume, which is sketched in Figure 3, at the Hydraulic Laboratory of the
320 University of Catania. The wave flume is 9 m long, 0.7 m deep and 0.5 m wide. At
321 the offshore end of the flume, a piston-type wavemaker generates regular waves.
322 At the onshore end, a porous beach is used to control undesired wave reflection.
323 At 5.5 m from the initial section of the flume, a Perspex sluice gate is used to
324 obtain a lock of salted colored water having a density equal to ρ_1 . Onshore of the
325 gate, the flume is filled with fresh water, having a density equal to ρ_0 .

326 The values of ρ_1 and ρ_0 are estimated for each test by using a set of three
327 calibrated 100-mL pycnometers, equipped with a thermometer having a precision
328 of 0.005C [21]. By following such a procedure, the error in measuring the density
329 is estimated to be smaller than 1 g/m³.

Fig. 3 Sketch of the wave flume in which lock-exchange experiments have been carried out.

330 Full-depth two-dimensional lock-exchange experiments have been performed
 331 both in the absence and in the presence of surface regular waves. In the first case,
 332 starting from an hydrostatic condition, the sluice gate is removed and a positive
 333 front of denser fluid intrudes in the lower part of the water column under the
 334 lighter fluid in the onshore direction while in the upper part a negative front of
 335 lighter fluid moves offshore. In the second case, the wavemaker starts generating
 336 monochromatic waves propagating in the onshore direction. As soon as the waves
 337 reach the sluice gate, the latter is removed and a gravity current develops. In this
 338 case, the propagation of the salted front in the onshore direction occurs in the
 339 presence of the wave motion. Acoustic wave gauges have been used to measure the
 340 characteristics of the waves, i.e. wave height H and wave period T , while a set of
 341 HD video cameras has been used to record the propagation of the density front at
 342 a frame rate of 50 fps, with 1920×1080 pixel wide images. A detailed description
 343 the experimental setup is reported in [21].

344 The presence of progressive surface waves causes a mean flow, producing a mass
 345 transport [15], which influences the propagation of gravity currents. The wave
 346 driven mass transport has two components: the Stokes drift due to irrotational
 347 free surface flow and the boundary layer component due to vorticity. The first

348 one is established immediately while the second one takes much longer, depending
 349 on the flume dimensions. In all the tests carried out, the duration of the tests is
 350 $O(10\text{ s})$. Such a duration is brief when compared to the time necessary for the
 351 development of a steady streaming component, about 5 min in the present case
 352 [18]. As a consequence, only the Stokes drift and consequently the offshore directed
 353 undertow influences the gravity current propagation, while the unsteadiness of the
 354 flow should play a negligible role. By means of Vectrino profiler measurements,
 355 it has been estimated that the undertow is about 0.6 cm/s, in agreement with
 356 predictions obtained by classic literature models [16, 4].

357 The characteristics of the benchmark experimental dataset used in the present
 358 work to calibrate the parameters of the numerical model are summarized in Ta-
 359 ble 1.

Table 1 Experimental benchmark tests used to calibrate the proposed numerical model.

Test n.	h	ρ_0	ρ_1	g'	H	T	H/L	U_m
	[m]	[kg/m ³]	[kg/m ³]	[m/s ²]	[m]	[s]	[-]	[m/s]
S004	0.200	997.856	1000.012	0.023	-	-	-	0.022
S007	0.200	998.857	1003.674	0.047	-	-	-	0.046
S009	0.200	998.705	1009.591	0.106	-	-	-	0.061
S111	0.203	997.781	1001.734	0.039	-	-	-	0.045
W004	0.200	998.141	1000.508	0.023	0.020	0.994	0.016	0.017
W007	0.200	998.857	1003.689	0.047	0.020	0.994	0.016	0.037
W009	0.200	998.705	1009.379	0.104	0.020	0.994	0.016	0.068
W123	0.202	997.704	1001.552	0.038	0.008	1.840	0.003	0.034
W108	0.200	996.242	1001.951	0.056	0.031	0.840	0.032	0.048
W109	0.201	997.804	1001.810	0.039	0.043	0.710	0.060	0.039

The first column indicates the name of the test, where the prefix S refers to classical lock-exchange tests while the prefix W indicates that density currents and surface regular waves have been combined. The second column reports the water depth h , the third and the fourth columns give the densities of the light and of the heavy fluids, namely ρ_0 and ρ_1 . The fifth column presents the reduced gravity g' . In the case of regular wave experiments the sixth and the seventh columns show the measured wave height H and wave period T . The eighth column reports the wave steepness H/L , in which the wave length L is computed by using the linear dispersion relationship, derived for surface wave motion under uniform density conditions [4]. Such a relationship has been used here since changes of the wave length in the presence of gravity currents are assumed to be negligible. Indeed the wave motion is dominated by gravity (g), while the gravity current is forced by reduced gravity g' , which is about two order of magnitude lower than g in the present case. Finally, the last column of Table 1 shows the measured time-averaged velocity of the heavy front U_m . This quantity is calculated as the slope of the straight line which best interpolates the front position over time, by considering just the constant-velocity stage. The position of the heavy front (from which velocity is computed) is measured by means of video image analysis. In particular, the initial frame is considered as a reference. The grayscale images are then converted into binary black and white images by using a threshold on the pixel intensity, to obtain the front as a set of black pixels. The front location is determined by counting the number of black pixels at the bottom, from the initial gate position. The errors on the location of the heavy front of the gravity current is smaller than 0.5 mm. Consequently the uncertainty on the measurement of time-averaged (bulk) velocity is always less than 10^{-4} m/s.

385 A preliminary analysis on the behaviour of the measured front velocities can
 386 be carried out as function of the Grashof number, similarly to [26]. Such a dimen-
 387 sionless number is the ratio between buoyancy forces and viscous forces:

$$Gr = \left(\frac{U_b h}{\nu} \right) \quad (24)$$

388 where $U_b = \sqrt{g'h}$ is the buoyancy velocity defined in terms of the initial wa-
 389 ter depth h . For large values of Grashof number ($Gr > 10^9$), viscous forces are
 390 negligible and the flow regime tends to become fully turbulent.

391 Figure 4 shows the behaviour of the heavy front bulk velocity as a function of
 392 \sqrt{Gr} , by separating still water tests from surface wave tests. It is evident that the
 393 presence of waves causes a reduction of front velocity, except for the tests having
 394 the greatest Grashof numbers, i.e. S009 and W009 ($Gr \approx 10^9$). It is possible
 395 to estimate a reduction of 15% of front velocity in the presence of waves, when
 396 $Gr < 6 \times 10^8$.

397 3.2 Numerical model setup and parameter calibration

398 The 2D computational domain is 14 m long and 0.3 m high, the still water depth
 399 is $h = 0.2$ m. At the offshore end of the numerical grid, an absorbing-generating
 400 boundary condition allows both the propagation of regular waves inside the domain
 401 and the absorption of reflected waves exiting the flume. At the onshore end, a
 402 sponge layer is used in front of a vertical wall to minimize wave reflection.

403 In the numerical simulations, several waves are run before the opening of the
 404 gate, in order to have an established wave field before the propagation of the
 405 density current. Although different from the experimental procedure, this is re-

Fig. 4 Averaged measured velocity of the heavy front as function of Grashof number square root, by considering both still surface and wave tests.

406 quired by the wave generation module, and it is numerically possible thanks to
 407 the separation between the wave module and the gravity current module.

408 The opening of the gate corresponds to the start of the gravity current in the
 409 numerical model. Initial conditions of such a model are: (i) density current velocity
 410 \mathbf{u}_d equal to zero; (ii) free surface elevation as obtained by the wave model; (iii)
 411 uniform density distribution at the two sides of the gate, with a density equal
 412 to ρ_1 if $0 \leq x \leq 7$ m, and to ρ_0 if $7 < x \leq 14$ m. The spatial discretization
 413 is different along the horizontal and vertical directions, in order to allow a fairly
 414 reasonable description of the vertical density profile along the tank. In particular,
 415 $\Delta x = 0.05$ m and $\Delta z = 0.015$ m.

416 The calibration of the numerical model has been performed considering both
 417 formulations of the turbulence closure, i.e. model A, where only a Smagorinsky-
 418 type of eddy viscosity $\nu_{t,A}$, function of C_s , is used, and model B, where a depth-

419 constant contribution, function of C_u , is also introduced to calculate $\nu_{t,B}$. In the
420 present work just the calibration of the coefficient C_s is discussed, which is shared
421 by both models. Indeed, the numerical results may be significantly affected by
422 the value of coefficient C_s introduced in the Smagorinsky formulation. Similar
423 analyses, not reported here for the sake of brevity, have shown that the numerical
424 results are less sensitive to changes of the coefficient C_u , which is kept constant
425 and equal to 0.008 in all the calculations discussed in the following.

426 In order to compare the numerical results with the experimental ones, the in-
427 terface between heavy fluid and ambient fluid is defined, in the model, as the part
428 of the domain in which density is equal to the mean value between that of ambi-
429 ent and of heavy fluid. Consequently, the heavy front position is the intersection
430 between the interface and the bottom. Figure 5 shows two examples of the com-
431 parison between the calculated and measured time evolution of the heavy front
432 position from the initial gate position, i.e. $x - x_0$.

433 Two tests carried out in the presence of the same reduced gravity $g' = 0.047 \text{ m/s}^2$
434 are considered, namely test S007 in the absence of surface waves (Figure 5a) and
435 test W007 in the presence of a superimposed regular wave motion (Figure 5b).
436 The results of both model A and model B are reported in Figure 5. It should be
437 noted that due to the relatively short length of the flume, in the present work the
438 gravity currents are analyzed only during the slumping or constant-velocity phase.

439 Calibration of the proposed numerical model has been carried out on the basis
440 of heavy front evolution. Indeed, this gives a bulk measure of the gravity current
441 dynamics, particularly during the constant-speed phase, and its measurements are
442 highly reliable. Density and velocity field are extremely difficult to be measured

Fig. 5 Examples of heavy front position from initial gate section ($x - x_0$) over time. Results of experiments and numerical simulations, with turbulent closure A and B, are superimposed; (a) test S007 without surface waves, $C_s = 2.47$ for model A, $C_s = 2.00$ and $C_u = 0.008$ for model B; (b) test W007 with surface waves having $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.994$ s, $C_s = 0.75$ for model A, $C_s = 0.78$ and $C_u = 0.008$ for model B. In both tests $g' = 0.047$ m/s².

443 over the entire flow domain. Their behaviour is significantly unstable, with the
 444 presence of non negligible turbulent structures (as K-H billows).

445 The optimal value of C_s has been determined by minimizing the value of the
 446 relative error Δ , calculated as

$$\Delta = \frac{U_s - U_m}{U_m} \quad (25)$$

447 where U_s and U_m are the simulated and measured time-averaged velocities of the
 448 front of the gravity current respectively, obtained for different values of the C_s
 449 coefficient. In particular, by considering the full dataset reported in Table 1, Fig-
 450 ure 6 (a) gives the errors obtained in the absence of waves, while Figure 6 (b) shows
 451 those obtained in the presence of waves. Similar plots are reported in Figure 7 for
 452 model B.

453 Although the phenomenon is strongly nonlinear, common trends exist and
 454 models A and B behave similarly, indicating also that the contribution of the
 455 depth-constant eddy viscosity is slightly beneficial, at least in the range of the an-
 456 alyzed values. First of all, as the value of C_s increases, the relative error decreases.
 457 Indeed, the larger the eddy viscosity, the smaller the predicted front velocity. If
 458 the simulated dissipation exceeds a certain threshold, the numerical model tends
 459 to underestimate the average front velocity and the relative error Δ becomes nega-
 460 tive. In the present work, an optimal value of C_s has been determined as the value
 461 of C_s at which $\Delta = 0$. It should be noted that such an optimal value is a function
 462 of the flow conditions. Indeed, while in both models the optimal values of C_s are in
 463 the range 2 to 10 in the absence of waves, when the wave motion is superimposed
 464 to the gravity current the optimal values of C_s are smaller as well as their range
 465 ($C_s = 0.04 - 4$). Hence, in general, even if g' is similar, smaller values of C_s should

Fig. 6 Error Δ as function of the C_s parameter, obtained for the optimization of model A:

(a) tests without waves; (b) tests carried out in the presence of surface waves.

Fig. 7 Error Δ as function of the C_s parameter, obtained for the optimization of model B:

(a) tests without waves; (b) tests carried out in the presence of surface waves.

466 be used when waves are present. This could be an indication of the fact that when
467 waves are superimposed to the current turbulence is reduced. In the latter case,
468 an additional role is played by the characteristic of the wave motion. Indeed, the
469 results indicate that for steeper waves the optimal value of C_s should be smaller.

470 Finally, in the presence of the smallest values of g' (e.g. tests S004 and W004,
471 $Re \approx 2000$), i.e. of very slow gravity currents, there is no difference between model
472 A and B. On the other hand, if the Reynolds number is larger than 2000, the
473 inclusion of the depth-constant contribution to the eddy viscosity in model B
474 leads to slightly smaller errors, if the same values of C_s are used in both models.

475 **4 Analysis of results**

476 The calibration procedure, described in Section 3, has been carried out consid-
477 ering only the heavy front position. Indeed, the eddy viscosity coefficients in the
478 numerical model have been chosen in order to adequately reproduce the inter-
479 face between the two fluids, particularly near the bottom of the flume. After such
480 a calibration procedure, in the present section the numerical model outputs are
481 used to describe the gravity current hydrodynamics by analyzing the distribution
482 of density, velocity, vorticity, shear stresses and entrainment. Such variables are
483 very difficult to measure during the experiments, but are readily available from
484 the numerical solutions.

485 As explained in Section 2, model results during the initial acceleration stage
486 after the opening of the gate may not be accurate, due also to the different exper-
487 imental and numerical procedures used to trigger the combined flow. The focus of
488 the present work is on the subsequent inertial constant-speed phase. Due to that,

489 numerical results on the evolution of the gravity currents are presented for $t > t_0$,
490 where the time scale t_0 is estimated on the basis of the equations for a falling body,
491 by considering the reduced gravity g' and a falling height $h/4$, which is equal to
492 the vertical distance between the centroids of the heavy fluid, respectively at the
493 instant $t = 0$ and during the slumping or constant-speed phase [9]:

$$t_0 = \sqrt{\frac{2(h/4)}{g'}} = \sqrt{\frac{h}{2g'}} \quad (26)$$

494 4.1 Density distribution

495 The time evolution of the spatial distribution of density ρ , which is the main
496 forcing of gravity currents and which gives a significant indication of the charac-
497 teristics of the gravity current hydrodynamics, may be qualitatively compared to
498 experimental findings obtained by means of flow visualization [21].

499 Density distributions, calculated by the numerical model using the turbulence
500 formulation A, are shown in Figures 8 and 9 for tests carried out without surface
501 waves (test S007) and in the presence of a regular wave motion (test W007),
502 respectively. Such tests have the same reduced gravity $g' = 0.047 \text{ m/s}^2$, thus the
503 different behaviour is caused only by the superimposition of surface waves. The
504 density distribution is shown at the gate section ($x = 7.0 \text{ m}$) in order to visualize
505 both the heavy front and the light one, which are directed respectively onshore
506 and offshore. The plots show the front during the constant-speed phase, i.e. for
507 $t > t_0 = 1.5 \text{ s}$. The time interval between each plot is 2 s, which corresponds to
508 two surface wave periods in the case of test W007.

509 The density distributions simulated by the model, both without and with sur-
510 face waves, show the presence of humps at the nearly horizontal interface between

Fig. 8 Results of model A, test S007 without surface waves. Density distribution at four time steps: (a) $t = 1.8$ s, (b) $t = 1.8$ s + $2T$, (c) $t = 1.8$ s + $4T$, (d) $t = 1.8$ s + $6T$, where $2T \approx 2$ s.

Fig. 9 Results of model A, test W007 with surface waves having $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.994$ s. Density distribution at four time steps: (a) $t = 1.8$ s, (b) $t = 1.8$ s + $2T$, (c) $t = 1.8$ s + $4T$, (d) $t = 1.8$ s + $6T$, where $2T \approx 2$ s.

the two fluids behind the steep front. The humps in the density distribution indicate the presence of turbulent structures which influence mixing between the two fluids, and whose size increases with time. Such a behaviour is evident in the absence of waves (see Figure 8 c and d), since in this case the horizontal front between the two fluids is characterized by the presence of alternating cells of high and low density close to the interface. It may be observed that the humps are larger in the rear part of both the heavy and the light fluid fronts. On the other hand, surface waves cause a reduction of the dimension of such structure between the fluids (see Figure 9). Indeed, in this case the mixing layer is smaller and more regular along the horizontal direction, and the dimension of the cells is influenced by the orbital velocity. In order to quantify such a phenomenon, the time-evolution of the maximum amplitude of the interface oscillations (i.e. humps) has been computed for the tests S007 and W007, which have the same reduced gravity. For the initially quiescent case S007 the highest hump over the time have an height equal to 0.085 m and its mean height is 0.045 m. In the presence of surface waves (test W007) the height of maximum humps is always lower than 0.07 m and its average value is in the range 0.030-0.035 m. From the above result, it can be argued that the presence of surface waves causes a 20-30% reduction of the maximum heights of interface oscillations. The result of the presence of waves reducing the thickness of the mixing layer is in agreement with visual observations of lock-exchange experiments reported in [21]. An additional quantitative investigation on mixing between the fluids is shown in Section 4.4.

533 4.2 Velocity and vorticity distribution

534 The analysis of the velocity and vorticity field may clarify what occurs at the
535 interface between the two fluids during gravity current propagation, particularly
536 focusing on the thickness of the mixing layer.

537 Figures 10 - 13 allow for a comparison of the velocity and the vorticity distri-
538 bution in the absence (test S007) and in the presence of waves (test W007), by
539 considering both turbulence closure models A and B, corresponding to the eddy
540 viscosity formulations reported in eqs. (22) and (23) respectively. In each of such
541 Figures the velocity field and vorticity distribution are plotted at four time steps
542 during two wave periods. The position of the interface between the two fluids is
543 also reported in the Figures. Such an interface is defined as the line along which
544 the density is equal to the mean value $(\rho_0 + \rho_1)/2$. In each plot the absence of
545 contour lines characterizes positive counterclockwise vorticity, while dotted curves
546 refer to negative clockwise vorticity.

547 It is possible to identify several features of lock-exchange hydrodynamics which
548 are not dependent on the presence of waves, since they also take place in the
549 absence of waves: the maximum values of counterclockwise vorticity are always
550 located across the interface between the two fluids. Such a primary mechanism is
551 more intense just downstream of the two steep fronts and it is weaker at the center
552 of the domain, where the gate is initially located. The reduction of vorticity is not
553 uniform, due to the development of Kelvin-Helmholtz (K-H) billows, at both the
554 heavy and light fronts. Indeed such K-H billows propagate in opposite directions
555 with respect to each front, gradually losing their intensity. Such an effect causes
556 the oscillation of the fronts, highlighted also in the experiments [21, 24].

Fig. 10 Results of model A, test S007 without surface waves. Vorticity distribution (gray scale with dotted contours for negative values), velocity fields (vectors) and front (separation between heavy and light fluid, represented by the thick line), at four time steps: (a) $t = 1.8$ s; (b) $t = 1.8$ s + $2T$; (c) $t = 1.8$ s + $4T$; (d) $t = 1.8$ s + $6T$ ($2T \approx 2$ s).

Fig. 11 Results of model B, test S007 without surface waves. Vorticity distribution (gray scale with dotted contours for negative values), velocity fields (vectors) and front (separation between heavy and light fluid, represented by the thick line), at four time steps: (a) $t = 1.8$ s; (b) $t = 1.8$ s + $2T$; (c) $t = 1.8$ s + $4T$; (d) $t = 1.8$ s + $6T$ ($2T \approx 2$ s).

Fig. 12 Results of model A, test W007 with surface waves having $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.994$ s. Vorticity distribution (gray scale with dotted contours for negative values), velocity fields (vectors) and front (separation between heavy and light fluid, represented by the thick line), at four time steps: (a) $t = 1.8$ s; (b) $t = 1.8 + 2T$; (c) $t = 1.8 + 4T$; (d) $t = 1.8 + 6T$ ($2T \approx 2$ s).

Fig. 13 Results of model B, test W007 with surface waves having $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.994$ s. Vorticity distribution (gray scale with dotted contours for negative values), velocity fields (vectors) and front (separation between heavy and light fluid, represented by the thick line), at four time steps: (a) $t = 1.8$ s; (b) $t = 1.8$ s + $2T$; (c) $t = 1.8$ s + $4T$; (d) $t = 1.8$ s + $6T$ ($2T \approx 2$ s).

557 The numerical results show also a secondary effect of the lock-exchange mech-
558 anism, which is perceptible both in the absence and in the presence of waves and
559 which is difficult to notice in the experimental data. A negative clockwise vortic-
560 ity cell develops ahead of each front. Such a cell is quite stable in time and it
561 counterbalances the primary counterclockwise cell located on the front. The two
562 cells, having positive and negative vorticity respectively, show similar dimensions
563 but the latter secondary cell is characterized by absolute values of vorticity always
564 lower than those of the primary cell.

565 The above described vorticity dynamics is general since it is not affected by
566 the presence of surface waves and by the adopted turbulence closure formulation.
567 However superposition of the wave motion to the gravity current propagation in-
568 duces a modification of the shape of both primary-positive and secondary-negative
569 vorticity cells. On the one hand the counterclockwise vorticity cells are more clus-
570 tered across the interface between the two fluids for test W007 compared to test
571 S007. On the other hand the clockwise cells are stretched under surface waves and
572 they tend to occupy the extreme part of the water column which is not covered by
573 the primary counterclockwise vortices. Both effects cause a reduction of the size of
574 vorticity cells, which is not counterbalanced by an increase of vorticity magnitude
575 within such cells. Thus the presence of surface waves always causes a decrease
576 in the total amount of vorticity. Since turbulence is highly related to vorticity, it
577 could be argued that the presence of surface waves causes a reduction of turbu-
578 lence intensity at the interface between heavy and light fluids. Such an effect is
579 similar to what happens in other flows characterized by wave current interaction
580 [14,19]. Furthermore, the presence of the waves reduces the front velocity. Such a

581 reduction, as well as the reduction of the intensity of vorticity, is an indicator of
582 the smaller buoyancy net effect induced by the wave orbital motion.

583 Concerning the two adopted eddy viscosity formulations, the difference between
584 the results obtained using model A and model B is negligible in the absence of
585 waves, as it can be noticed from the comparison between Figure 10 and 11. Also the
586 comparison between the two models in the presence of waves (see Figures 12 and
587 13) shows that the hydrodynamics simulated by the two models are qualitatively
588 similar. Nevertheless, in such cases the values of vorticity given by model A are
589 slightly greater than those computed by model B. Furthermore, model B allows a
590 better matching of numerical results with experimental measurements, as it has
591 been already shown when studying the front position, in Figure 5.

592 The intra-wave effect of the orbital motion on the gravity current hydrodynam-
593 ics can be investigated considering Figures 14 and 15, in which the vorticity and
594 velocity field are plotted at each $T/4$ during a wave cycle, for turbulence closure
595 models A and B respectively.

596 In both formulations the dimension and the position of the positive vorticity
597 cells have a weak dependency on the wave phases and are clustered at the interface
598 between the two fluids. On the other hand the secondary counterclockwise vorticity
599 cell located ahead of the heavy front at the bottom tends to be stretched and it
600 is forced to enter the region between the positive cells and the free surface, when
601 the wave crest passes over the positive cells. This phenomenon can be observed in
602 plot (a) of both Figures 14 and 15. Conversely, the negative vorticity cell located
603 at the left of the domain (within the heavy fluid) tends to touch the bottom when
604 the wave trough passes over it and it goes up when the wave crest appears.

Fig. 14 Results of model A, test W007 with surface waves having $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.994$ s. Vorticity distribution (gray scale with dotted contours for negative values), velocity fields (vectors) and front (separation between heavy and light fluid, represented by the thick line), at four time steps spaced by $T/4$: (a) $t = 5.8$ s; (b) $t = 5.8$ s + $T/4$; (c) $t = 5.8$ s + $T/2$; (d) $t = 5.8$ s + $3/2T$.

Fig. 15 Results of model B, test W007 with surface waves having $H = 0.02$ m, $T = 0.994$ s. Vorticity distribution (gray scale with dotted contours for negative values), velocity fields (vectors) and front (separation between heavy and light fluid, represented by the thick line), at four time steps spaced by $T/4$: (a) $t = 5.8$ s; (b) $t = 5.8$ s + $T/4$; (c) $t = 5.8$ s + $T/2$; (d) $t = 5.8$ s + $3/2T$.

605 As for the difference between the two turbulence formulations, it is possible
 606 to notice that the results of model A, shown in Figure 14, give greater positive
 607 vorticity values with respect to the ones of model B, shown in Figure 15. Con-
 608 versely, the behaviour of negative vorticity cells is not influenced by turbulence
 609 closure formulation. Such an effect is probably related to the fact that turbulence
 610 affects more the gravity currents and less the wave motion, at least in the case of
 611 non-breaking waves, as the ones in the present work.

612 4.3 Shear stresses

613 As noticed when discussing the results in Figures 12 and 13, the presence of the
 614 waves induces a general reduction of the vorticity intensity. This turns into a
 615 reduction of the intensity of the shear stresses along the water column.

616 The spatial distribution of the shear stresses τ has been derived by the velocity
 617 field. In particular, here, just the contribution of the gravity current has been
 618 estimated as

$$\frac{\tau}{\rho} = (\nu + \nu_t) \left(\frac{\partial u_d}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w_d}{\partial x} \right) \quad (27)$$

619 where ρ is the local value of density.

620 The spatial distribution of the shear stresses, not shown here for the sake
 621 of brevity, reflects that of the vorticity distribution. Indeed, large negative shear
 622 stresses are clustered in cells along the interface between the two fluids. Isolated
 623 cells of positive shear stresses are located in regions having clockwise vorticity.
 624 In general, the intensity of the shear stresses is reduced in the presence of surface
 625 waves. In order to provide an overall estimate of such a reduction, Figure 16 shows

626 the space-time-averaged value $\overline{\tau/\rho}$ as a function of the root square of the Grashof
627 number of the tests, which represents the turbulence levels of the gravity current.

628 The results of models A and B are similar. Indeed, in both cases it may be no-
629 ticed that: (i) $\overline{\tau/\rho}$ increases with a parabolic law as the Grashof number increases;
630 (ii) in the presence of waves, the values of $\overline{\tau/\rho}$ are smaller. Moreover, the shear
631 stresses computed by model B under surface waves are more regular than those of
632 model A, since they are close to the interpolation function.

633 Once again, the latter results indicate that the combined flow undergoes a
634 reduction of shear stresses induced by the waves, as observed in [14,19]. Such an
635 effect increases as the Grashof number increases.

636 Finally, as before, the results obtained by the two turbulence models collapse
637 for the undisturbed gravity current propagation. If a wave motion is added to
638 the propagation of the current, model B predicts appreciably larger average shear
639 stresses. Such behaviour is a confirmation that the turbulence enhancement intro-
640 duced by the depth-uniform contribution to the eddy viscosity plays a role only in
641 the presence of the orbital motion, which contributes to stirring up momentum.

642 4.4 Entrainment

643 In order to give a quantitative estimate of mixing between heavy and ambient
644 fluid, the results of the optimized model (turbulence closure B) have been used to
645 calculate the entrainment coefficient E , by following the procedure shown in [21].
646 In particular, E is defined as the ratio between the bulk velocity of the ambient
647 fluid entering into the heavy fluid (w_e) and the relative horizontal bulk velocity of

Fig. 16 Specific mean shear stress $\overline{\tau/\rho}$ as a function of the square root of the Grashof number Gr : (a) results of model A; (b) results of model B.

648 the heavy and light front:

$$E = \frac{w_e}{u_s - u_l} \quad (28)$$

649 where u_s and u_l are the velocities of the simulated heavy and light front, computed,
650 respectively, by dividing the position from the gate of the heavy and of the light
651 front by the time t . All the velocities considered in eq. (28) are bulk-averaged at a
652 given time step. The velocity w_e is evaluated by considering the volume of ambient
653 fluid V mixed with heavy fluid. Such a volume is computed by subtracting the
654 initial volume of heavy fluid from the total volume below the interface between
655 the two fluids at time t . To this aim, in this case the interface is defined as that
656 part of the domain in which the concentration $C = (\rho - \rho_0)/(\rho_1 - \rho_0)$ is equal
657 to 0.02. Therefore, the entrained velocity w_e is obtained as the ratio between the
658 bulk entrained discharge V/t and the width of the flume multiplied by the length
659 of the interface between the two fluids.

660 The time evolution of the entrainment coefficient E is shown in Figure 17, for
661 quiescent ambient fluid tests and wave tests having similar g' . It is possible to
662 notice that mixing is always very intense at the initial stages and afterwards tends
663 to reach a steady condition. In the tests this occurs 6 s after the opening of the
664 gate.

665 The most important result shown in Figure 17 is that the presence of surface
666 waves causes generally an increment of entrainment and consequently of mixing
667 between the two fluids. In particular, such an increase of entrainment, due to
668 waves, is reduced in time and it is, on average, 33% for $t > 6$ s.

669 A physical justification of the increment of entrainment under surface waves,
670 notwithstanding the reduction of turbulence, vorticity and shear stresses, is related

Fig. 17 Time evolution of the entrainment coefficient E for tests carried out in the absence of waves and with various wave slope H/L . $g' \approx 0.05 \text{ m/s}^2$.

671 to the presence of the orbital motion under surface waves. Indeed, the vertical
 672 component w_B of the orbital velocity has non-zero values across the interface
 673 between the two fluids, thus increasing the amount of ambient fluid entrained into
 674 the heavy fluid.

675 The increment of wave slope (H/L) causes greater instabilities in the entrain-
 676 ment coefficient, since mixing is more influenced by the smaller wave trajectories
 677 and faster orbital velocities. Quantitatively, the wave slope does not have a lin-
 678 ear effect on entrainment computed at the end of simulations ($t > 12 \text{ s}$), i.e. in
 679 steady conditions. In particular, in the tested conditions such a final entrainment
 680 reaches its minimum value, about 0.045, in the absence of waves (test S007). The

681 maximum value of entrainment at the end of simulation is reached for the test
682 W109, having the steepest surface waves ($H/L = 0.06$). Such an upper limit of
683 E oscillates around the value 0.07. All the other surface wave tests, having lower
684 wave slopes, causes entrainment coefficients which follow between the two limits
685 discussed above.

686 5 Conclusions

687 The presence of surface waves causes several effects on gravity currents. In particu-
688 lar, the present work analyzes the wave influence on: shape of the interface between
689 the two fluids, mixing, turbulence, velocity and vorticity fields. Such aspects are
690 studied by means of an efficient modeling approach, which uses two separated
691 models for surface wave and gravity current propagation respectively. In such a
692 modeling system the total velocity is decoupled into a wave-related component
693 and a density-gradient-related component. The latter accounts for the presence
694 of the gravity currents. Turbulence is described by two alternative approaches,
695 based on the eddy viscosity concept: the first approach considers a simple subgrid
696 Smagorinsky formulation (model A); the second one contains both the Smagorin-
697 sky formulation and a depth-uniform eddy viscosity (model B).

698 Calibration of the model was carried out with experimental lock exchange tests,
699 proving that the inclusion of the depth-uniform eddy viscosity into a Smagorin-
700 sky formulation (i.e. model B) is beneficial, particularly under combined gravity
701 current-surface wave flow, when Reynolds number of gravity current is larger than
702 2000.

703 The choice of the calibration parameter C_s , related to the Smagorinsky formu-
704 lation, is a critical point for the proposed modeling system. This is mainly related
705 to the simplicity of the model, which has been developed as an engineering-oriented
706 tool. For such a reason, a great attention has been paid to the calibration of the
707 model before its application for investigating the effects of surface waves on lock-
708 exchange hydrodynamics. Further works will be focused on a physically-based
709 optimization of the value of C_s and on its effects on the results.

710 The results of the model showed a reduction in the average velocity of the front
711 under surface waves, in accordance to the experimental outcomes. Also the front
712 oscillations under waves evaluated by the model are similar to those oscillations
713 that are measured. The evolution of the density distribution over time highlighted
714 that the presence of waves causes a reduction of irregularities at the interface
715 between the two fluids. The vorticity fields showed the existence of a region of
716 positive counterclockwise vorticity along the interface. An overall decrease of the
717 total amount of vorticity was registered if the gravity current propagated in the
718 presence of surface waves. Concurrently, a significant reduction of the turbulent
719 shear stresses was observed under waves, which reaches values of about 37% (for
720 model B), at the greatest tested Grashof number, i.e. for $\sqrt{Gr} = 3 \cdot 10^4$.

721 The reduction in the amount of turbulence and vorticity of gravity current, due
722 to waves, would lead us to presume that mixing is less intense under waves. Nev-
723 ertheless the estimation of entrainment highlights that the surface orbital motion
724 causes an increase of mixing. Therefore such a phenomenon is not only related to
725 the turbulence of the gravity current, but also to the wave motion itself. In detail,
726 due to the vertical component of orbital velocity lighter fluid particles from the
727 higher region cross the interface, thus forcing the mixing between the two fluids.

728 Future work will be aimed at extending the range of wave conditions, supported
729 also by new experimental tests, in order to better simulate the interaction of surface
730 waves and turbulent structure at the front.

731 **Acknowledgements** This work has been partly funded by the Italian Ministry of Education,
732 Universities and Research MIUR through the Research projects of significant national interest
733 - PRIN 2010-2011 - project name HYDROCAR (cod. 20104J2Y8M_003) and the PRIN 2012
734 project Project "Hydro-morphodynamics modelling of coastal processes for engineering pur-
735 poses" (cod. 2012BYTPR5), through the PO FESR SICILIA 2007-2013 Axis IV Operational
736 Objective 4.1.2 Intervention lines 4.1.2.A project MedNETNA and through the EU funded
737 project HYDRALAB PLUS (proposal number 64110).

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